

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Managing Human Reference Atlas Registrations

Creating, publishing, and organizing tissue block-level RUI registrations for the Human Reference Atlas

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Introduction

Spatially registering tissue data is critical for constructing a three dimensional human reference atlas (HRA) (Börner et al. 2025, 2021). The HRA Registration User Interface (RUI) (Börner et al. 2022) captures the size, location, and rotation of tissue blocks in three dimensions, along with other metadata. Two separate SOPs exist to detail procedures for tissue registration by surgeons, clinicians, and others via a data portal, such as the HuBMAP or SenNet Ingest Portals ([Using the Embedded Registration User Interface](#)) or using the [Standalone Registration User Interface](#).

This standard operating procedure (SOP) outlines the procedures for creating, publishing, and organizing tissue block-level RUI registrations in the HRA Registrations GitHub repository. It is intended primarily for internal use by the HRA Registration Coordinator (RC). Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**. Resources such as templates, spreadsheets, GitHub repositories, and other materials that are used to implement the procedures are listed in **Table 2**.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Registration Coordinator (RC)** works with Tissue Data Providers to register tissue samples, maintains the HRA Registrations GitHub repository, and updates trackers to report .

Tissue Data Providers provide spatial and donor data for tissue samples. They review and hold final responsibility for ensuring the correct assignment of spatial and donor information for experimental data used in the Human Reference Atlas.

The **Technical Director** leads the development and provisioning of the HRA Registration tools: the HRA Registration GitHub repository, the RUI, the RUI Locations Processor, and the Exploration User Interface (EUI).

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Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Registration Coordinator	Nancy Ruschman	infoccf@iu.edu
Technical Director	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
Tissue Data Providers	various	various

Relevant Resources

Table 2. Resources used in these procedures.

Name	Purpose	Location
HRA Registrations GitHub repository	RUI registrations are collected here	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-registrations
RUI Email Templates	Serves as a guide for common communications with Tissue Data Providers	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RuHo8MWDkm8g5aQufOXcFCae_2TgfeP5E3axwn-o_0/edit?tab=t.0
RUI Actionable Tracker	Tracks the status of datasets as they move through the registration pipeline	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1puEnF5w38F11zrav9R8jKWjAx_5UYqhtSM5sQUvJtBw/edit?gid=393253914#gid=393253914
ORCID	Register for an ORCID	https://orcid.org
Tissue Registration Issues form	Captures situations where registration may be difficult or impossible and provides guidance for handling these issues	https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1wn2Xc7DnY5yfs8SLFr43nWDdF3hyxLGp6K-0w4ynLg/viewform?edit_requested=true&pli=1
HRA - RUI Locations Processor README file	Instructions for installing the registrations processor, writing YAML files,	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-rui-locations-processor/tree/main#readme
GitHub style guidelines	Guidelines for how to write commit messages	https://git.kernel.org/pub/scm/git/git.git/tree/Documentation/SubmittingPatches?h=v2.36.1#n181

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Registrations Schema	The YAML schema used to create a registration set by combining metadata from the publication, donors, and extraction sites	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-rui-locations-processor/blob/main/registrations.schema.json
Controlled vocabulary for technology	Use these terms for consistent use of terminology related to assay technology	https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/hra-registrations/blob/main/controlled_vocabulary/technology.yaml
Exploration User Interface (EUI)	Use this interface to view registrations	https://apps.humanatlas.io/eui

Naming Conventions

Collection names are critical for condensing key information and creating a clear and consistent folder structure in the repository. The naming convention below serves this purpose and should be followed diligently.

Schema

Name each collection according to the following schema: <portal name>-<organ name>-<author surname>-<year>. Components should be articulated in all lowercase and separated by dashes.

- For example, a registration set from the HCA consortium with heart data from a publication led by Nathan Tucker that was published in 2020 is named hca-heart-tucker-2020.

Exceptions

- Additional dashes: In some cases, additional dashes may improve readability. This is applicable when portal or consortium names contain a dash (e.g. “SEA-AD”), or organ names comprise multiple words (e.g., “large intestine” or “bone marrow”).
- Duplicate names: In the unlikely event of duplicate names, append an alphabetic character for differentiation, e.g., uiowa-eye-mullins-2023a, uiowa-eye-mullins-2023b, uiowa-eye-mullins-2023c.
- Nonstandard characters: To avoid encoding issues and maintain system compatibility, replace characters that are not part of the standard English alphabet—such as accents, tilde, and other diacritics—with their closest standard equivalent (e.g., björklund becomes bjorklund).

Component naming guidelines

- <portal name>: Use the abbreviated name of the portal or consortium when available. For registration sets derived from independent publications, replace [portal name] with

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either na or an applicable descriptor, such as the university or research institute name, e.g., uiowa-eye-mullins-2023a.

- <organ name>: Use names that align with the latest version of the Uberon standard. When the data set contains tissue from multiple organs that form a higher-level organ (e.g., the small intestine and the large intestine making up the intestine), use the higher-level name. If the data set contains tissue blocks from an assortment of organs, use pan instead of individual organ names
- <author surname>: Use the surname of the Tissue Data Provider with whom you are in contact.
- <year>: Use the four-digit year in which the digital object was assigned a DOI.

Procedures

Requesting registration

- Tissue Data Providers or HRA experts can email the HRA RC to request the registration of one or more datasets, see Table 1 for contact information. Form submissions auto-populate an internal Google Sheet that the RC reviews periodically.
- The RC reviews requests to ensure their data is supported by the current version of the HRA (e.g., a 3D reference model exists) and establishes initial communication with the Tissue Data Provider.
- The RC introduces the HRA registration process and asks to be connected with an appropriate Tissue Data Provider to schedule a registration session. Email templates are available here: [RUI email templates](#).
- The outcome of this procedure is the establishment of contact between the RC and Tissue Data Provider.

Creating registrations

- If the Tissue Data Provider shows interest in registering their data on the HRA, the RC creates a new entry in the [RUI Tracker](#). This entry will be used for tracking the status of the registration process and should be regularly updated. The process follows the Getting Things Done project management workflow.
- All registration sets live in two tabs in the Tracker, one general and another specific.
 - The general location is the All tab, a reliable repository of every registration set the RC has worked with. Maintaining a comprehensive record is useful for avoiding duplications and locating the status of ongoing registrations.
 - The status-specific location depends on the current status of the registration. **Table 3** provides an overview of the various tabs in the Tracker, their logic, and key data points.

Table 3. The various tabs in the RUI Tracker

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Tab	Qualifying Registration Projects	Key Data Points
Inbox	Projects with unclear status	Set name
Actionable	Projects where the next action is clear	Set name, Next Action
Waiting For	Projects blocked on someone/something	Set name, Waiting on (who/what), Due by
Published	Projects that completed registration	Set name
Archived	Projects that failed registration	Set name, Reason for failure

- Note: The registration set name should follow CNS GitHub naming protocol described in the Naming Conventions section below.
- The RC and Tissue Data Provider discuss two scenarios for proceeding with registrations:
 - Collaborative registration takes place over a video conference meeting, where the Tissue Data Provider works with the RC on the registration. During this call, the RC shares their screen and steers the registration process with input and feedback from the Tissue Data Provider.
 - Independent registration is completed by the Tissue Data Provider in their own time and the RC assists with technical support in case of problems.
- To ensure accuracy, the RC should cross-check metadata received from the data provider against the publication's metadata available as supplementary information.

Registration meeting checklist for collaborative registration

When a registration meeting is scheduled, ensure the following information and resources are gathered prior to the call.

- Obtain the Tissue Data Provider's ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID), a unique identifier that ensures proper attribution of contributions.
 - If the Tissue Data Provider does not have an ORCID, they can obtain one [here](#).
- Obtain metadata associated with the dataset, which should include:
 - Donor details: age, sex, and other relevant data
 - Dataset URL: deep links to sample-specific datasets (e.g., CellxGene, GEO, Figshare, HuBMAP, etc.).
 - Optional: review the organ online to ascertain important components such as size, shape, anatomical structures.

During registration process

- Verify the previously gathered details, i.e, the ORCID and the metadata that is being registered with the Tissue Data Provider.
- If the Tissue Data Provider is registering for the first time:
 - Show a sample registration. Preferably, select a previously completed registration of the same organ (if available).

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- Clarify the concept of anatomical structure (AS) tags and their relevance.
- Inform the author that the actual sample size can differ from the Block Shape represented in the RUI. Clarify that in certain cases, estimates or best guesses can be used for the location of the block placement.
- If the Tissue Data Provider asks about what the HRA is and its goals, explain that the goal of the HRA is to provide a standardized coordinate framework for human biology.
- General Registrations
 - Specify the minimum metadata required for registration, (donor sex, age) and details on the collected samples — indicating which and how many donors correspond to each RUI location.
 - If special cases arise, obtain the author's permission and proceed to record the meeting for reference.
- The outcome of this procedure is one or more RUI location JSON files.

Enriching registrations

The RC completes the following steps.

- Request access to the [repository](#) from the Technical Director.
- Use a code editor (preferably [VSCode](#)) to install the HRA RUI Locations Processor.
 - Follow this [README file](#) for instructions.
- Initialize a new registration set in the staging folder of the repository.
 - In the command-line interface, navigate to the staging folder.
 - Use the New command in the HRA RUI Locations Processor to create a new registration set, consisting of a repository folder and its default contents.
 - Note: The folder name should follow CNS GitHub naming protocol described in the Naming Conventions section below.
- Integrate RUI location files into the repository.
 - Rename the RUI registration JSONs appropriately and move them to the Registrations sub-folder of the registration set.
 - Commit the changes to the git repository using a clear commit message.
 - Note: When writing commit messages, follow GitHub's [style suggestions](#) and write the message in the present-tense imperative, i.e. as a command.
 - If not on the main branch of the repository, submit a pull request to main to integrate your changes.
- Add metadata to RUI location files.
 - Following this [schema](#), edit the registrations.yaml file to populate it with tissue provider metadata.
 - Refer to this [markdown file](#) to learn more about writing YAML files for HRA registrations.

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- Note that every unique provider must have a unique Version 4 Universally Unique Identifier (UUID). This is a unique identifier for each tissue provider.
- Refer to this [YAML file](#) to verify that the technology field in the metadata complies with the required format.
- Create a dataset thumbnail (optional)
 - Create an Assets subfolder inside the relevant folder in the repository.
 - Add the thumbnail, an 800x600 pixel image file, to the Assets subfolder.
 - The image file's pathname must match the pathname of the thumbnail value in the YAML file.
- Merge location and provider information.
 - Use the Normalize command in the HRA RUI Locations Processor to generate the rui_locations.jsonld file.
 - Commit the changes to the repository using a clear commit message.
 - If you are not on the main branch, submit a pull request to integrate the RUI locations.
- Validate the registration set with the Tissue Data Provider.
 - Generate a custom EUI with only the new registration data by appending the registration set's name to the following link:
<https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/hra-registrations/staging>.
 - Share the link with the Tissue Data Provider for validation
 - In case the Tissue Data Provider requests changes to the registration set, work with them to incorporate their revisions.
 - In case there are issues with the registration, e.g., tissue laterality is unknown, the RC records this information in this [Google Form](#).
- The outcome of this procedure is a validated registration set.

Publishing the registration set

The RC completes the following steps.

- If this is healthy data, move the registration folder from staging to the root folder of the repository and add it to the federated collection. If it is diseased data, move the folder inside the diseased folder in the repository.
- Navigate to the registrations.yaml file of the federated folder or the federated\diseased folder. These are unique YAML structures comprising imports from other collections.
- Add the name of your registration set to the sorted list.
- Run the normalize command on the federated collection
- The outcome of this procedure is the publication of the registration set, which should be accessible via the [EUI](#).

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References and Resources

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Glossary

anatomical structure (AS): An anatomical structure is a distinct biological entity with a 3D volume and shape, for example, an organ, functional tissue unit, or cell.

Exploration User Interface (EUI): An interface developed by MC-IU to explore tissue, see <https://portal.hubmapconsortium.org/ccf-eui>.

registration set (see also dataset graph): Grouping of tissue blocks by the study or paper in which they were published. Each set has a human-readable registration set name, a machine readable Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI), and it links to a paper DOI and tissue block IDs.

RUI Locations Processor: A command line tool the RUI workflow uses to integrate tissue mapping data into the HRA's common coordinate system. The Locations Processor takes `registrations.yaml` and individual JSON files as input and generates a `ruil_locations.jsonld` as output.

tissue block: A sample or specimen derived from an organ or tissue including subsections thereof obtained from a donor that has a unique ID and links to donor, organ extraction site, processing, preservation and other metadata. The locations of tissue blocks are registered using the Registration User Interface.

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